

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SALICYLOYL-HYDRAZIDE CHELATES AT 35°

Cation	Medium H ₂ O : dioxane	Ionic strength	Log K ₁	Log K ₂	Log K ₃	Log β _n
H ⁺	50:50	0.01	9.10	—	—	9.10
		0.05	9.07	—	—	9.07
		0.10	9.05	—	—	9.05
		0.15	9.03	—	—	9.03
UO ₂ ²⁺	50:50	0.01	8.76	6.20	—	14.96
		0.05	8.64	6.16	—	14.80
		0.10	8.42	6.30	—	14.72
		0.15	8.12	6.20	—	14.32
Y ³⁺	50:50	0.01	5.93	5.20	4.23	15.36
		0.05	5.45	4.80	4.02	14.27
		0.10	5.40	4.75	4.00	14.15
		0.15	5.10	4.46	3.82	13.38
La ³⁺	50:50	0.01	5.06	4.19	3.56	12.18
		0.05	4.50	3.72	3.14	11.36
		0.10	4.58	3.68	3.06	11.32
		0.15	4.43	3.54	3.05	11.07
Ce ³⁺	25:75	0.01	5.40	4.54	—	9.94
		0.05	5.18	4.44	—	9.62
		0.10	5.28	4.54	—	9.82
		0.15	5.16	4.72	—	9.88

decreased solubility. The extent of association of ions decreases more in the case of Ce³⁺ as compared to Y³⁺, La³⁺ and UO₂²⁺. Accordingly this accounts for the lower stability of cerium complexes.

References

1. K. E. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALM and M. B. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1027.
2. M. ITO, *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, **58**, 11346 h.
3. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
4. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous solution", P. HAASE & SON, COPENHAGEN, 1941.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HASS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
8. E. HUCKEL, *Physik Z.* 1925, **26**, 93.
9. B. S. SEKHON and S. L. CHOPRA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1975, **10**, 21.

Chalcones XIV : Potential Germicides Derived From Acetyl Naphthalene

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DURING recent years many homocyclic¹⁻⁶, and heterocyclic^{8,14} chalcone analogues have been reported to possess bactericidal, fungicidal, germicidal^{9,10}, analgesic¹¹, antiinflammatory, sedative¹¹ carcinogenic⁷, etc. activity. Marked bactericidal⁷ activity is exhibited by naphthalene, phenanthrene chalcones

and also by 2-furfurylidene acetophenone and 2-thienyl styryl⁸ ketones. These observations have prompted us to synthesise naphthyl chalcones. This paper is in continuation^{4-6,9,10,13,14} of our programme to study the structure activity relationship of 2-naphthyl chalcones as potential germicides.

In view of the well known physiological activity of phenanthrene and anthracene chalcones it was thought desirable to synthesise nineteen naphthyl chalcones with the expectation of enhanced activity. Also, that naphthalene compounds are easily scattered over the system owing to its increased lipid solubility and, therefore, a good contact with the disease germs is possible.

The compounds were synthesised by condensation of 2-acetylnaphthalene with substituted benzaldehydes according to the general procedure described earlier⁶. The condensation of 2-acetonaphthone with chloro-, methyl-, and methoxy benzaldehydes gave well crystalline products with 25% alcoholic caustic potash solution at room temperature within 24 to 36 hrs. whereas the condensation with hydroxy benzaldehydes under these conditions produced only viscous tarry masses from which no crystalline compound could be obtained. It may be due to resinification and other side reactions of hydroxy benzaldehydes with concentrated alkali solution. It is interesting to note that condensation of 2-acetonaphthone with nitrobenzaldehydes in presence of the same concentration of alkali solution gave immediately dark coloured compounds of unknown composition, whereas condensation at low temperature (10°-15°) with 5% alkali solution produced well crystalline yellow compounds.

The compounds thus synthesised are listed in Table 1 and are characterised by their physical properties, halochromism with concentrated sulphuric acid, by preparing 2 : 4-DNPS of a few compounds and elemental analyses. The analyses of the elements (Table 1) were within ±0.5% of the theoretical value. All melting points are uncorrected.

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TABLE 1

R	Colour and Crystal form	M. P. °C		Yield %	Halochromism with Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Analyses	Dia. of Zone of inhib. in mm.
		Chal.	2 : 4 sDNP				
2-OH	Violet needles ^b	142	—	32	brown	C, H	—
3-OH	Brown plates	117	—	29	dark brown	C, H	—
4-OH	Violet globules ^a	140	—	34	pink	C, H	—
2-Cl	Canary yellow needles	148	228	79	red	C, H, N	11
3-Cl	Yellow prism,	114	193	72	dark red	C, H, N	10
4-Cl	Yellow plates	146	237	81	Orange	C, H, N	9
2-NO ₂	Plates yellow	137	—	64	blood-red	C, H	8
3-NO ₂	Yellow plates	139	215	61	red	C, H, N	8
4-NO ₂	Yellow needles ^a	147	205	67	violet	C, H, N	7
2-OMe	Yellow Globules ^b	145	—	58	orange	C, H	—
3-OMe	Yellow clusters	152	219	54	red	C, H, N	—
2-Me	Brown needles ^a	128	—	47	pink	C, H,	—
3-Me	Yellow prisms ^b	138	211	43	brown	C, H, N	—
4-Me	Yellow needles	146	—	48	red	C, H	—
2, 3-OMe ₂	Yellow plates	166	254	56	orange	C, H, N	—
6-Br-3, 4-OMe ₂	Yellow needles	148	—	64	violet	C, H	9
5-Br-4-OH-3-(OMe)	Yellow prism	154	—	42	red	C, H	7
2, 4-(OH) ₂	Brown globules ^b	48	—	28	brown	C, H	—
4-NMe ₂	Canary yellow needles	110	—	53	orange	C, H	—

Benzoic Acid

Crystallised from : a=Ethyl acetate
b=Benzene

11

The germicidal activity of the naphthyl chalcones was screened at a concentration of 100 to 150 µg/ml. of 50% aqueous-ethanol against *S. aureus* and *E. Coli* by following agar-cup method. The inocula for the test were 24 hours old and were prepared from stationary culture. The results are reported in Table 1. by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition in mm. and compared against benzoic acid.

Experimental :

The compounds reported have been synthesised by following the method of Misra^{1,4} et. al. One typical example is cited below :

Equimolar quantities of 2-acetonaphthone and 2-chlorobenzaldehyde were dissolved in aldehyde free alcohol and condensed in presence of 25% alcoholic caustic potash solution at room temperature. The excess of alkali was neutralised with hydrochloric acid at ice temperature and the resulting compounds purified through repeated crystallisations from alcohol unless otherwise mentioned. The purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatographic Technique as reported earlier^{1,2}.

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References

1. S. S. MISRA and BHOLA NATH., *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1972, 35, 95.
2. S. C. KUSHWAHA and J. B. LAL., *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, 32, 208.
3. W. B. GEIGER and J. E. CONN., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 112.
4. S. S. MISRA and S. C. KUSHWAHA., *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, (India), 1970, 40, 301.
5. S. S. MISRA., *Labdev J. Sci. & Tech.* (India), 1971, 8A, 222.
6. S. S. MISRA and BHOLA NATH., *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 260.
7. M. KAMODA., *J. Agr. Chem. Soc.*, Japan 1954, 28, 791.
8. S. C. KUSHWAHA and DINKAR., *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1967, 5, 82.
9. S. S. MISRA and DINKAR., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 629.
10. S. S. MISRA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 335.
11. K. K. HSU and F. C. CHEN., *Tai.-Wan K' O Hsueh*, 1973, 27, 236.
12. D. N. DHAR and S. S. MISRA., *J. Chromatog*, 1972, 69, 416.
13. S. S. MISRA., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 68.
14. S. S. MISRA and S. C. KUSHWAHA., *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, (India), 1971, 40A, 468.